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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: ROLE OF LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA

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Abstract :

The paper analyzes the linkages between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) in the rendering social service context. In particular, it explores and discusses the role and characteristics of responsible insurance business within Life insurance in India, focusing on the impact of sociological and other factors. Through an empirical analysis, the paper aims in fact to understand whether and to what extent the institutional structure influences the adoption of socially responsible practices within the Life insurance Corporation of India. Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to the obligations and duties of business to the society. CSR, if implemented in true sense, helps in enhancing the quality of stakeholders and the society at large. This paper is the outcome of descriptive study conducted with the purpose to assess the various CSR initiatives undertaken by LIC such as Education Facilities, Medical and healthcare and General public utilities -2013-14 etc., to uplift the unprivileged section of the society and also made an attempt to study the effect of CSR on life insurance business of LIC and on its various stakeholders. The study will provide innovative ideas in designing new strategies, policies and roadmaps which can effectively help in achieving the main objectives of an organization through appropriate CSR schemes and it enhances not only goodwill but also contribute to more profit by doing honest efforts and ethical business practices. The present paper is solely depends on secondary sources and scope is confined to LIC is the main limitation. The study concludes that CSR are now quite an integral part of LIC objectives and becomes an effective tool by which a corporation can differentiate itself from their competitors and holds strong position in the market.

Keywords : *CSR, Corporate Social Responsibility, LIC, Stakeholders*

Introduction :

Many different definitions exist of CSR. They are as diversified as the activities that claim to be part of it. This paper chooses to adopt Michael Hopkins' definition, according to which "Corporate Social Responsibility is concerned with treating the key stakeholders of a company or institution ethically or in a responsible manner. 'Ethically or responsible' means treating key stakeholders in a manner deemed acceptable according to international norms. Social includes economic and environmental responsibility. Stakeholders exist both within a firm and outside. The wider aim of social responsibility is to create higher and higher standards of living, while preserving

the profitability of the corporation, for peoples both within and outside the corporation." Although corporate India is involved in CSR activities, the government is working on a framework for quantifying the CSR initiatives of companies to promote them further. According to Minister for Corporate Affairs, Mr. Anurag Kumar, government is developing a system of CSR credits, similar to the special carbon credits which are given to companies for green initiatives. Moreover, in the government made it mandatory for all public sector oil companies to spend 1% of their net profits on corporate social responsibility. Besides the private sector, the government is also ensuring that the public sector companies participate actively in CSR initiatives. The Department of Public Enterprises (DPE) has prepared guidelines for central public sector enterprises to take up important corporate social responsibility projects to be funded by 2-5 per cent of the company's net profits. 4 Today, CSR has gone beyond merely charity and donations, and is approached in a more organized fashion. It has become an integral part of the corporate strategy. Companies have teams that devise specific policies, strategies and goals for their CSR programs and aside budgets to support them. These programs, in many cases, are based on a well-defined social philosophy or are closely aligned with the companies' business objectives. This study would help in understanding the benefits and present situation of CSR projects of LIC. The study will provide innovative ideas in designing new strategies and roadmaps which can effectively help in achieving the main objectives of the organization through appropriate CSR schemes.

Company Profile of LIC :

The Parliament of India passed the Life Insurance Corporation Act on the 13th June 1956, and the Life Insurance Corporation of India was created on 1st September 1956, with the objective of spreading life insurance much more widely and in particular to the rural areas with a view to reach all insurable persons in the country, provide them adequate financial cover at a reasonable cost. LIC continues to be the dominant life insurer even in the liberalized scenario of Indian insurance and is moving fast towards new growth trajectory surpassing its own past records. LIC has issued over 100 policies during the current year. LIC has crossed many milestones and has unprecedented performance records in various aspects of life insurance business.

Need of the Study :

In today's cut throat market competition the evolving concept of Corporate Social Responsibility is gaining wide acceptance and popularity all across the globe. LIC recognized as an effective tool to maintain balance between both business and social. LIC with long back history of more than five decades has played a very prominent

role in the society. Various CSR initiatives undertaken by LIC has benefited a large population of India in ways of education, health, medical, housing development, upliftment of poor through insurance schemes. Further, this study would help in understanding the benefits and present situation of various CSR projects of LIC.

Literature Review :

McWilliams & Siegel (2001) define CSR as 'actions that appear to further some social good, beyond the interest of the firm and that which is required by law'. This voluntariness should however not be a substitute to regulation or legislation concerning social and environmental standards (Hediger, 2010). Rajesh C Jampala and Bh Venkateswara Rao (2005) examined the role of LIC in Corporate Social Responsibility. The study found that CSR, if implemented in true sense will enhance the quality of stakeholders and the society at large.

De Prins *et al.* (2009) list four driving forces for companies to initiate a CSR process:

- CSR as an instrument for damage and risk control and for reputational management;
- CSR as a business opportunity;
- CSR as a product of the vision of an ethically motivated leader;
- CSR as a product of a company's core values.

Objectives of the Study :

The Present paper is basically concerned with the following objectives.

- To examine the nature and extent of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives under taken by of Life Insurance Corporation and to study its relevance in business.
- To study the overall impact of corporate social responsibility schemes on financial performance of Life Insurance Corporation.
- To study the benefits of the corporate social responsibility initiatives taken by Life Insurance Corporation.

Research Hypotheses :

The study tests whether the selected variables of LIC are significant or not during the study period. These specific hypotheses are tested at appropriate time while analyze and interpreting the results. The following hypotheses have been taken to put on test.

H₁: There is a relationship between Total Income of LIC and amount granted towards CSR Sanctions.

H₂: There is a positive and significant relationship between Profitability of LIC and expenditure incurred towards CSR.

Consumers:
 The customer has a choice from a variety of products and gets an appropriate insurance coverage at affordable prices. CSR enhances the practice of doing business ethically and thus there would be lesser chances of mis-selling.

Government:
 Tax is the main source of government income. LIC pays a large amount of tax government in the form of taxes. The tax collected by the Govt. is used for society and developmental projects of the economy.

Life Insurance Business:
 The performance of LIC has been increased manifolds after the implementation of various CSR programmes. The LIC New Policies Business crossed to 3886372 and total premium income reached to Rs. 186077.31 crore during the financial year 2010-11.

Year	Education	Medical	Public Utility	Total
2008-09	7955000	5150000	2700000	15805000
2009-10	24138673	19603639	14411503	58153815
2010-11	24414892	37662748	8932129	71009769
2011-12	44014274	23975201	9107110	77096585
2012-13	10096264	33360024	754094	44210382
Average	22123820.6	23950322.4	7180967.2	53255110

Social Responsibilities Vision IN 2012:
 It has been the constant endeavor of the Corporation to provide security to people as possible and to channelize the savings mobilized for the welfare of the at large. To meet this end, the Corporation has been promoting social welfare investments in Infrastructure and Social Sector which includes:

- * Projects/Schemes for generation and transmission of Power,
- * Housing Sector,
- * Water Supply and Sewerage Projects/Schemes,
- * Development of Roads, Bridges & Road Transport

The total Investment in these sectors during 2012-13 was ` 27,398.10 crore as per Table The investments as at 31.03.2013 by way of Central, State and Government Guaranteed Marketable Securities, Loans, Debentures & Investments in Infrastructure and Social Sector amounts to ` 8,19,835.28 crore

Table-2, CSR Grants of LIC
 Source: Annual Reports of LIC Figure-1

The Table No. 2 Represented that the CSR Grants of LIC for the past five years from 2009-2013 it can seen. All three kinds of grants are in fluctuating trend. During the year 2011-12 corporation has done more grants comparatively rest of years. Public utility grants are almost nil during the years 2013.

Table-3, Profitability and CSR Performance of LIC

Year	Total Income	PAT	Sanctioned Amt.	CSR Spend Amt.	Total Income to Sanctions	PAT to Spend
2008-09	20636298.11	84462.59	900000000	920720760.7	2.3	0.009
2009-10	20028065.25	95734.88	-	20123800.13	-	0.47
2010-11	29872154.51	106071.68	-	29978226.19	-	0.35
2011-12	29927263.1	117180.37	-	30044443.47	-	0.39
2012-13	28731538.36	131334.29	1000000000	1028862873	2.87	0.012
Average	25839063.87	106956.762	950000000	405946020.6	2.59	0.246

Source: Annual Reports of LIC

Figure-2

Table No. 3 Profitability and CSR Performance of LIC. It is seen two times been done during the year 2008-09 and 2012-12 and average of total sanction is 2.59 percent PAT to CSR Spend ratio lies in between 0.009 to 1.0 and average of this ratio is 0.246 percent only during the study period.

Testing of Hypotheses:

In this paper the researcher has made two hypotheses are used to test Corporate Social Responsibility and Performance of LIC. Whereas, for computing the appropriate t value to test the correlation significance. The formula for computing the appropriate t- value is to test significance of a coefficient. It employs the t distribution:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

The degrees of freedom for entering the t-distribution is N - 2. Table-2) i.e. 3 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 2.306 for two tailed hypotheses are re-stated as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H₀): There is a relationship between Total Income of LIC amount granted towards CSR Sanctions.

Table-4, Correlation and t-test result for Total Income and CSR Sanctions

Total Income to Sanctions	r value	r ²	Correlation result	t value	Hypothesis result
1.00	1.00	1.00	Perfect correlation	-	Carry

Source : Computed

Table 4 depicts the Correlation between Total Income and CSR sanctions of LIC. It can be seen that total income and sanctions showed positive and perfect relationship with total income. Whereas, by t-test results is nil. Consequently, the null hypothesis is not yet to be decided. There is no relationship could be ascertained in between impact of Total Income and CSR sanctions during the study period.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀): There is a positive and significant relationship between Profitability of LIC and expenditure incurred towards CSR.

Table-5, Correlation and t-test result for Profitability and expenditure incurred towards CSR

PAT to CSR Spend	r value	r ²	Correlation result	t value	Hypothesis result
0.116	0.014		Positive and Significant	11.92111	Accepted

Source : Computed

Table 5 depicts the Correlation between Profitability and Expenditure towards CSR of LIC. It can be seen that profitability and expenditure incurred towards is CSR positive. Whereas, by t-test results, it is clear that the computed value of hypothesis is less than the critical value of t at 5% level of significance. As a result the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the relation is positive and significant. There is an impact of profitability with expenditure incurred towards CSR.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

The concept of corporate social responsibility has gained prominence from all over the world. Organizations must realize that government alone will not be able to get success in its endeavor to uplift the downtrodden of society. LIC is one of the oldest and leading life insurance company in India has been contributed impressively high in various socio-economic development projects through appropriate CSR schemes. Presently, many group insurance and social security schemes such as Janashree Shree Yojana, Swarna Jyanti Gram Swarajgar Yojana, Social Security Group Insurance Schemes, Krishi Samraksh Samajik Suraksha Yojana, Critical Illness Rider, Mann Ammi Bina Yojana many more CSR projects has been undertaken by LIC for the welfare of poor and spreading insurance to under penetrated rural population who cannot afford to pay premium. In addition, the corporation is providing different services such as education, medical and public utility. With the implementation of new schemes and CSR initiatives, the performance of LIC has been improved noticeably high in rural areas where private players are yet not reached. CSR activities have their advantages. The benefits are in terms of building a positive image, encouraging social involvement of employees, which in turn develops a sense of loyalty for the organization.

This study presents the major findings of the CSR initiatives of over a period of years from 2008-2009 to 2012-2013. The following observations were found and are discussed here under.

- It is observed that corporation has sufficient funds to meet its risk and generates more funds and utilized purposefully,
- LIC of India is an effective control of Non Performing Assets over its Advances
- It observed that corporation net profit per employee performance is improved to year.
- Net profit after tax of the corporation has been decreased year 2010 to year 2013. It is observed assets quality is not satisfactory during the study
- It is found that more liquidity has been maintained by LIC during the year. It is observed that Liquidity Position is satisfactory.

To conclude, our findings from the operational and financial performance of LIC of India are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that LIC of India should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets and improving the productive efficiency of employees. Profitability of the insurance and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency in addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction cost and management of funds are very much influenced to the corporation for better performance.

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